

GRP-PIPE FITTINGS PRODUCED ON A COMPUTER CONTROLLED FILAMENT WINDING MACHINE

G. MENGES, E. A. HILLE

*Institut für Kunststoffverarbeitung an der RWTH Aachen
Pontstraße 49, 5100 Aachen, West-Germany*

GRP-Pipe fittings in most cases are hand made, and therefore the quality is not that good and reproducable as it should be. In this paper methods are described, how pipe tees as well as elbows can be produced automatically on a computer controlled filament-winder. Control data are recorded on a special coordinate measuring device and afterwards translated into the code of the filament winder. Machinery equipment necessary to do this is described.

1.1 PRESENT POSITION

Particularly in the field of winding techniques, machine developments at the IKV and by machine manufacturers have opened up possibilities over the last few years for producing more complex cores e. g. cores that are not rotationally symmetrical. It is above all the use of microprocessors or process computers and also numerical controls 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 for controlling the winding process which have considerably increased the flexibility of the machines and, with the elimination of mechanical controls, have made it possible to produce more complex patterns.

1.2 DETERMINING THE CONTROL DATA

Of major importance in this is the determination of the control data for the winding process. For rotationally symmetrical cores, the control data can be determined by computer programs, but because of the scope involved, these can generally only be run on large computers 5'.

If more complicated cores like pipe fittings for example have to be produced which are no longer rotationally symmetrical, then the time needed for the theoretical calculation of the control data increases considerably and normally involves such high costs that the use of the winding technique is very quickly jeopardized.

The method of the experimental determination of control data for geometrically complex cores has therefore proved to be perfectly suitable.

In order to be able to fully exhaust the technical possibilities of winding machines, a system was developed which enables control information to be determined without the direct use of a production plant. At the heart of the system is a special coordinate measuring desk, which has the same degrees of freedom as the actual winding machine 6 Fig. 1.

The filament control is movable in three spatial directions, with the fourth axis being the rotational axis of the core. All four movements can be controlled by hand, whereby the paths covered in each axis are recorded by special measuring devices. With this setup, it is possible to copy previously determined winding patterns on a core. The coordinate measuring desk is connected via a multiplexer with a process computer, which, at an interval previously selected by software, stores discreet points of the pattern and subsequently converts them into the machine code of the numerically controlled winding machine.

Fig. 1 Digitizer to determine control data for filament winding

Fig. 2 Recording the control data via a coordinate measuring

1.3 FILAMENT CONTROL AND IMPREGNATION

In order to make the winding process more economical, the number of rovings or the width of the band being processed should be as large as possible. When producing complex cores, this necessitates a special band-or filament control which also enables a band of constant width to be laid down on curved surfaces. This is achieved by making the exit gap of the payout-eye rotatable. This rotating movement could be controlled just like all the other movements, although this does increase the cost of determining the control data fairly considerably. For this reason, filament control elements 7 were developed, which automatically bring about this rotating movement via a control system. For this, use was made of the knowledge, that through the pre-tension of the adjacent filaments or the band, force components are produced across the band if the band pushes closer together and the width decreases. These force components exert a transverse force on the band guide element (which can, for example, be ascertained with a bending beam provided with a strain gauge strip) or they make the band shift to the side in the guide slit (this is indicated, for example, by light barriers). Via a regulator and an angle correcting element, the guide element is controlled in such a way by the measuring recorder that there are no more transverse force and no shifting of the band to one side. There is then no change in the width of the band on leaving the filament control unit. Fig. 3 shows some possible designs for sensors of this kind. Depending on the particular application, these sensors can then be mounted onto the winding unit.

Fig. 3 Sensors

For special applications, the exit slit has to be continually rotated at angles greater than 360° . This necessitated the construction of a special impregnation unit. A band pulled through a flat channel filled with resin causes dragging of the flow and thus a pumping effect. By means of lateral openings at the beginning and end of the channel, the resin can be made to circulate via a bypass running parallel to the impregnating pipe. If the cross-section of the channel is suitably designed, there will only be a very low flow velocity in the bypass, with the result that the resin, which has collected a large amount of air in the impregnation channel, can be freed of gas. The flat rectangular impregnation channel is provided with sealing elements at the points where the roving enters and exits. Where the resin goes in and goes out, there is a circular arrangement to ensure that the impregnation channel can be rotated.

Fig. 4 Tape leading and impregnation unit for numerically controlled winding machine

1.4 PRODUCTION OF PIPE FITTING

With this setup, it is even possible to produce complicated pieces such as T-shaped pipes on a numerically controlled or computer-controlled winding machine. In doing this, it has proved useful to make a division into basic windings. Fig. 5 shows a few possible windings of this kind. These basic windings are recorded one after the other with the aid of the coordinate measuring device and stored. They can then be combined with one another in such a way that complete and uniform winding of the surfade is achieved.

Fig. 5 Basic windings on pipe-tees

Pipe bends can also be produced on a winding machine of this kind. It is preferable to select a clamping arrangement such as that shown in Fig. 4. To determine an optimum winding pattern for pipe bends, the following mathematical considerations have to be made:

A 90° elbow (without connecting pieces) represents a section from a torus which, as a whole, represents a rotationally symmetrical body. For rotationally symmetrical cores according to 5, the Clairaut relationship applies. This states that the product of the radius of the body and the sine of the winding angle on this radius must be constant for a geodesic winding:

$$C = r_i \cdot \sin \alpha_i$$

where

$$r_i = \text{radius of body at the point } i$$

calculated on the symmetry axis of the torus

and

$$\alpha_i = \text{winding angle}$$

According to this relationship, a winding angle distribution on the torus surface can be determined, as is shown in Fig. 6 8. The winding angle distribution which is ideal from the strength point of view (exposure to internal pressure) and at the same time geodesic can be obtained from the relationship:

$$C_{opt} = n \cdot \sin \alpha_{opt}$$

$$C_{opt}: \text{Clairaut constant standardized to pipe radius}$$

$$n = \frac{\text{radius of curvature of the bend}}{\text{radius of the Pipe}}$$

$$\alpha_{opt} = \text{winding angle at } r = R$$

$$R = \text{radius of curvature of the elbow}$$

Fig. 6 Possible winding angle distribution on 3 D pipe bends

α_{opt} should be selected as 36° for the internal pressure load, which corresponds to an angle of 54° when related to the bending line of the elbow. If the winding angle distribution (Fig. 6) is known, then the winding pattern and the machine movements for winding the pipe elbow can be fixed with the aid of the teach-in system.

Decomposable cores are used both with T-pipes and for curved pipes. The T-pipes are rounded off at the transition zone and this considerably reduces the flow resistance. The core segment at the transition zone was made of rubber and because of its flexibility, can be easily deformed after the straight pipe-shaped parts have been removed with a take-off device.

The cores of the curved pipes are also decomposable, with the straight ends having to be demoulded first after separating the pole caps of the winding. The actual bended section can then be separated into four parts and taken out through the resultant pole openings.

For the production of curved pipes made of GRP, another alternative has been developed, based on winding onto a flexible core standing under internal pressure 9. To begin with, a cross winding (e.g. winding angle = 54°) is put onto a core of this kind. (In order to prevent the resin from dripping, the core ought to be rotated after the bending process. But this is not possible because of its flexibility. For this reason, the winding is best covered with a pre-tensioned rubber tube by the process described in Fig. 7. This can be followed by bending and fixing. Curing is best carried out in a hot salt solution, which has the same density as the resin.

Fig. 7 Setup for applying a flexible covering to fix the matrix during curing.

REFERENCES

- 1 N. N., information from "Baer Co.", Weingarten, W. Germany
- 2 N. N., Technical Paper from "McLean-Anderson Co."
- 3 N. N., information from "Bolenz und Schäfer Co.", W. Germany
- 4 K O B E R, J. F., "Microcomputer controlled Filament Winding", paper for the 34th Annual Technical Conference, 1979 SPI New Orleans
- 5 B A R K I N G, H. L., Dissertation, Technical University RWTH Aachen, 1978
- 6 K I M M E R L E, G., unpublished scientific work, IKV-archives -No. SA 7834
- 7 Projekt Patent of IKV "S e n s o r e n", Nr. 79/11901 - P 2933709.5
- 8 B R U C K M A N N, G., unpublished scientific work, IKV-archives-No. SA 7938
- 9 Projekt Patent of IKV "R o h r k r ü m m e r" Nr. 79/12234 - P 2937377.1